

Compressive strength predictions for carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles: Imaging modalities for quantifying the detrimental effect of fibre misalignments

O.V. Ferguson^{a,b,*}, J.B. Jørgensen^a, L.P. Mikkelsen^{b,*}

^a*LM Wind Power, Jupitervej 6, Kolding, 6000, Denmark*

^b*Department of Wind Energy, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, 4000, Denmark*

Abstract

This study compares two modelling strategies for predicting the compressive strength of thick unidirectional carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles at the meso-scale. Two-dimensional and three-dimensional approaches are considered, incorporating realistic fibre distributions obtained from optical microscopy and X-ray computed micro-tomography, respectively. Fibre volume fraction and orientation distributions are quantified through image processing and used as input for finite element models. A homogenised elastic-plastic constitutive model is employed to predict the compressive strength associated with kink-band formation. The fibre distributions derived from both imaging modalities exhibit comparable characteristics, with average through-thickness fibre misalignments of approximately 0.45° . However, the X-ray data reveal significant in-plane misalignments with location dependency, and average deviations up to 0.93° . Model predictions are compared against uniaxial compression tests of the pristine material, though experimental values proved conservative due to challenges in load introduction. The 2D models produced predictions close to the experimental results, with kink-band failure initiating near through-thickness fibre misalignments. In contrast, the 3D models predicted compressive strengths 50-69% higher than experimental values, with failure associated with localised regions

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: olen@dtu.dk (O.V. Ferguson), lapm@dtu.dk (L.P. Mikkelsen)

of severe fibre misalignment and reduced fibre volume fraction. It is concluded that 2D micrograph-based models are insufficient for accurately predicting the compressive strength in the pristine material. Instead, 3D fibre distributions are essential to capture the local deviations that govern the onset of compressive failure in carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles.

Keywords: Fibre volume fraction, Fibre orientation, Kink band failure, Image-based simulation

1. Introduction

Thick Unidirectional Carbon Fibre-reinforced Pultruded Profiles (UDCFPP) are used in the spar cap design of large wind turbine blades. The change from conventional fabric-based composites was based on an incentive to improve the stiffness, strength and fatigue performance of the material used for load-carrying components [1]. However, as presented by Budiansky and Fleck [2], carbon fibre-reinforced composites are notoriously sensitive to fibre misalignments relative to the primary load direction, and the compressive strength can easily be reduced by 50-60 %.

There is thus an incentive to characterise the compressive behaviour of thick UDCFPPs and investigate the potential risk of strength reductions associated with manufacturing-induced fibre misalignments. However, due to a high fibre volume fraction, typically ranging from 60-70 %, and the high strength of carbon fibres, it is increasingly challenging to characterise the compressive strength experimentally, often resulting in conservative results due to load introduction initiated failure [3]. Analytical and numerical solutions are, thus, essential to support the characterisation of the compressive strength and to study the governing parameters leading to failure.

Compressive failure of polymer-based fibre-reinforced composites is typically associated with fibre microbuckling in the form of a kink band. In an attempt to characterise the critical microbuckling strength, Argon [4] and later Budiansky and Fleck [2] associated plastic shear deformation of the matrix with an instability of the fibres, resulting in kink band formation. The models are based on a constant idealised fibre

misalignment within a predefined band and do not enable the analysis of realistic fibre orientation distributions. It does, however, pave the way for understanding the governing material parameters affecting the compressive strength. More realistic fibre distributions were later considered by Kyriakides et al. [5], where observations from micrographs of a thin carbon pre-preg material were used as inspiration for a 2D Finite Element (FE) model with alternating matrix and fibre layers. An idealised spatial fibre distribution was used to study the effect of local variations related to, e.g., variable amplitude fibre orientation and variable fibre volume fraction distributions, resulting in compressive strength predictions close to experimental results. Although it enables the analysis of more realistic fibre distributions, it is limited by the idealised spatial fibre distribution in a plane.

Yerramalli and Waas [6] developed a similar approach for 3D analysis of idealised fibre distributions, investigating the effect of the fibre diameter on the microbuckling strength by accounting for the bending stiffness of the fibres, which have been shown to affect the compressive strength for short wavelength fibre misalignments [7]. To characterise realistic fibre distributions, Emerson et al. [8] developed a method capable of tracking individual fibre paths using X-ray Computed micro-Tomography (μ CT), resulting in a volumetric fibre orientation distribution. Using this capability, Takahashi et al. [9] developed a 3D FE-model with discrete fibres embedded in a matrix including realistic fibre orientations. The model was limited to a cylinder with a diameter and length of $\approx 60 \mu\text{m}$ and $340 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, containing 40 fibres in the volume, where both constituents were discretised using second-order continuum elements in AbaqusTM. Considering this small volume of interest, the total simulation time required to obtain a solution for the compressive behaviour was around 300 hours on a standard laptop. A new strategy to reduce the computation time for micromechanical models was recently developed by Bikos et al. [10]. They use a combined beam and shell meshing strategy for the fibres and matrix, respectively, demonstrating the efficiency and accuracy for a Field of View (FOV) containing 75 fibres. Compared with a baseline using 3D continuum elements with a resulting simulation

time of around 180 hours, they improve the computational efficiency by 99.8% with only a 6% error from the baseline. With this significant reduction in computation time, they stated that the method can be applied to larger subsets up to a couple of thousand fibres, bridging the micro- and meso-length scale. However, micromechanical methods are still limited in size when considering thick pultruded profiles with hundreds of carbon fibre tows containing tens of thousands of filaments per tow. Wilhelmsson et al. [11] presented a 2D FE-model based on fibre orientation distributions estimated from micrographs to study the compressive behaviour of Non-Crimp Fabrics (NCFs). They include the full thickness ranging from 1.5 - 2 mm, and a length of 20 mm, including the natural undulations occurring in NCFs. The model shows high prediction accuracy in characterising the compressive strength of fibre-reinforced composites, where the dominating fibre orientations can be simplified to a 2D representation. The compressive strength predictions are based on a fracture mechanics approach that requires knowledge about interfacial strengths and energy release rates, which can be challenging to characterise.

Jeppesen et al. [12] presented a distinct difference in orientation distribution due to the manufacturing characteristics of NCFs and UDCFPPs. They use the image processing method, structure tensor analysis, on X-ray μ CT data to estimate volumetric fibre orientations. For NCFs, they demonstrate large periodic through-thickness orientations with a standard deviation $\approx 4.5^\circ$. In contrast, orientations in UDCFPP are randomly distributed along the principal material axis with a through-thickness standard deviation $\approx 1.2^\circ$. Due to a random orientation distribution in the UDCFPP, a 2D representation of the orientation distribution cannot necessarily be used to accurately predict the compressive strength, as failure may be governed by local deviations and not periodic orientation distributions.

Considering the challenges in characterising the compressive strength of thick UDCFPPs experimentally, and the observations regarding randomly distributed fibre orientations, this work compares compressive strength prediction methods based on 2D and 3D representations of realistic fibre distributions. Similar to the work presented

by Wilhelmsson et al. [11] and Jeppesen et al. [12], fibre orientation distributions are estimated from different imaging modalities, namely optical microscopy and X-ray μ CT aimed for 2D and 3D simulation, respectively.

The methods presented here are based on an updated version of a previous work by the authors in [13], where X-ray μ CT data were used to predict the compressive strength based on volumetric fibre orientation distributions only. The updated methods include the fibre volume fraction distribution estimated from image characteristics. A Non-linear constitutive model developed for 2D and 3D by Christoffersen and Jensen [14] and Skovsgaard and Jensen [15], respectively, are used for predicting compressive failure by kink band formation. The constitutive model is based on homogenised elastic-plastic material properties from the fibres and matrix material and enables the analysis of Large Fields of View (LFOV) with representative fibre orientation distributions at the meso-scale.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Material system and failure mode

This work is based on the UDCFPP, presented in Figure 1a. Compared with a NCF used for the same application, the UDCFPP is designed to increase the specific stiffness and strength by enhancing the fibre content and alignment along the main load-carrying direction (x-axis).

Similar to the results observed by Wilhelmsson et al. [16] for NCFs, the UDCFPP fails in compression due to kink band formation. An experimental study is presented in this work for UDCFPPs with a series of compression tests. Section 2.7 presents details about the experimental campaign where most of the samples fail in the tapping regions, and measurements are, thus, considered conservative. Nevertheless, it should be mentioned that it is experimentally hard to make such a high-quality material test fail in the gauge section. Attention is here directed to the failure mode presented in Figure 1b, where kink band failure occurs beneath the tabbing region. The proposed

Figure 1: Unidirectional Carbon Fibre-reinforced Pultruded Profile.

compressive strength prediction method is thus associated with the through-thickness kink band failure mechanism in Figure 1b.

2.2. Compressive strength prediction method

Figure 2 presents the overall method used for predicting the compressive strength based on different imaging modalities. The method is divided into three parts. (a) Generation of a FE-model based on realistic fibre distributions quantified from 2D or 3D images, to simulate static compression. (b) Experimental characterisation of constituent properties used in a non-linear constitutive model for simulating the elastic-plastic response, and finally, (c) FE simulations to predict the compressive strength based on realistic fibre distributions.

The workflow presented in Figure 2a illustrates the method available in a co-submitted Software Impact publication [17]. All steps from handling image data acquired using optical microscopy or X-ray μ CT, to simulating static compression with a linear-elastic material model are presented in a Code Ocean Notebook, and shared in a GitHub repository. A short introduction to the workflow in Figure 2a is presented: Regardless of the imaging modality, the method starts with image acquisition of the sample of interest. Fibre volume fraction, $V_f(x, y)$, and fibre orientation distributions, $\phi_{xy}(x, y)$, are determined based on the contrast between constituents. These

Figure 2: Compressive strength prediction workflow presented using data from a micrograph. (a) Generation of image-based FE simulation model with realistic fibre distributions, available in [17] (Sections 2.3 - 2.5). (b) Experimental characterisation of constituent properties used in a non-linear constitutive model for predicting the kink band formation (Section 2.6). (c) FE simulation to predict the compressive strength based on realistic fibre distributions (Section 3). Stress-strain relations are normalised with respect to a reference strength defined later.

field quantities are mapped to a FE-mesh through integration point-wise mapping. Material properties and orientations are updated according to the field quantities at each integration point. A static compression simulation is then used to investigate the stress-strain distribution for the material of interest. Due to differences in image characteristics for the two imaging modalities investigated here, the resulting output is compared in Sections 2.3 - 2.4.

2.3. Imaging modalities

Ideally, the compressive strength prediction method should be based on the pultruded profile’s representative volume/plane. The distribution of fibres in the volume of a pultruded profile was studied in [12] and [18] for carbon and glass fibres, respectively. They present an inhomogeneous fibre distribution, where fibres are clustered in regions with intermediate resin-dominated regions.

The representative volume/plane should thus reflect the inhomogeneous distribution to avoid conservative estimates due to the impact of local imperfections. Considering this observation, the following sections present the applied acquisition methods, X-ray μ CT and optical microscopy.

2.3.1. X-ray computed micro-tomography

Based on the above observation, samples used for X-ray scanning should have a cross-section representing the global fibre distribution without compromising the spatial resolution to an extent where fibre features vanish. As the objective is to compare the capabilities of two modelling approaches and not predict the compressive strength for the entire UDCFPP, this study has been limited to modelling sub-volumes.

Four scans have been performed on a ZEISS XRadia 410 Versa using absorption contrast with the settings shown in Table 1. Figure 3 illustrates four volumes of interest, with two central scans and two scans covering the material near the surface. Samples are extracted from the UDCFPP by grinding to the desired thickness, followed by cutting them to the desired length and width, resulting in $100 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ samples.

Table 1: X-ray μ CT scan and reconstruction settings on a ZEISS XRadia 410 Versa.

Sample names	Exposure time	Total scan time per sample	Binning	Accelerating voltage
(C50, C75, S50, S75)	4 s	6 h	1	40 kV
Power	Optical magnification	Voxel size	Field of view	Number of projections
10 W	4 \times	1.51 μm	3 mm ³	3201

Figure 3: Sample cutouts from UDCFPP with regions of interest highlighted and named according to position, e.g., central scan 50 mm along the width direction (z-axis) is named C50. Samples are cut from the same profile where the surface scans are located in the same width coordinate, further down the x-axis.

The fibre orientation distribution was studied in [12, 13], where it was shown that fibres are well aligned with the pultrusion direction and that fibres are closely packed, resulting in a high V_f . As fibre characteristics are determined based on the contrast between the matrix and fibres, a high level of detail is required, and the voxel size should thus be based on the fibre dimensions. With an approximate carbon fibre diameter of $7\ \mu\text{m}$, a voxel size of $1.5\ \mu\text{m}$ was chosen, which yields an appropriate resolution and contrast. Binning 1 with a 2000×2000 pixel resolution for the flat panel detector was used to cover the whole cross-section of the samples.

Following a 3D reconstruction of the X-ray scans, a 16 GB voxel-based image with intensity information at every voxel is obtained. The 3D reconstruction is based on 3201 2D radiographs acquired around the x-axis, and results in the cylindrical dataset presented in Figure 4a. The dataset is cropped to the dimensions required for the FE-model as presented in Figure 4b. A 2D representation of the dataset is presented in Figure 4c, where slices of three orthogonal planes show the fibre distribution in the volume together with a zoomed image of a fibre showing the image resolution relative to the fibre features.

Figure 4: X-ray μ CT dataset from the central scan, C50.

2.3.2. Optical microscopy

Unlike 3D X-ray μ CT scanning equipment, optical microscopes are more accessible, offering options for fast acquisition of high-resolution images with a LFOV. Therefore, the sample used for optical microscopy considers the full thickness of the pultruded profile. Samples of $25 \times 5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$ (length, thickness, width) were cut from the profile and cast into an epoxy resin block. Sample preparation was performed on a Struers Tegramin-30 grinding and polishing machine using a four-step grinding procedure. An initial step using grit 500 with water suspension, followed by two steps using grit 1200 with 9 and $3 \mu\text{m}$ diamond suspension, respectively. Finally, a polishing step using $1 \mu\text{m}$ diamond suspension resulted in a surface with a clear contrast between the carbon fibres and matrix material. An optical light microscope, Leica

Figure 5: LFOV micrograph of a UDCFPP in the xy -plane. All ROIs are of size $[x, y]=[4083, 2722]$ pixels, corresponding to an area $\approx [2377, 1583]\mu\text{m}$, similar to the xy -dimensions of the X-ray μCT data in Figure 4c.

DMI5000-M, with an XY-stage for translating the sample, was used to acquire high-resolution images. A mesh of 8×24 overlapping images with a pixel size of $0.58 \mu\text{m}$ was acquired and subsequently stitched to produce an LFOV image with the dimensions $23 \times 5 \text{ mm}$. For this article, the image has been cropped to $10 \times 5 \text{ mm}$. Figure 5a presents the LFOV image, which is divided into an array of 3×4 Regions of Interest, ROI, with similar through-thickness dimensions as the X-ray μCT datasets used for predicting the compressive strength. Micrograph ROI-11 is presented in Figure 5b with a zoomed section showing the image resolution relative to the fibre features.

2.4. Field quantity determination

As presented in the short introduction to the overall method in Figure 2a, the compressive strength predictions are based on fibre distributions using fibre volume fraction and fibre orientation as field quantities. A detailed description of the methods applied for the determination of field quantities can be found in the supplementary paper [17]. The following sections briefly introduce the methods used, focusing on the differences in field quantity characteristics for the two imaging modalities.

2.4.1. Fibre volume fraction distribution

The distribution of the fibre volume fraction, V_f , for the two imaging modalities is estimated using an image segmentation procedure. Constituents are separated based on their grayscale intensity distribution, in which the contrast between constituents governs the accuracy of the estimated V_f distributions. Referring to the grayscale intensity distributions for the micrograph and X-ray μ CT data in Figure 6a and 6b, respectively, a clear distinction between the fibres and matrix is observed for the micrograph, but the X-ray μ CT data has a skewed normal distribution that includes all features in the data. Thus, the micrographs are more suitable for estimating the V_f distribution without prior knowledge about the material's global mean fibre volume fraction, \bar{V}_f . However, to match the global stiffness in the data with the measured stiffness from the compression tests (see Section 2.7), the segmentation procedure reduces the error between the image \bar{V}_f^{image} and the burn-off test $\bar{V}_f^{burn-off}$.

The segmentation procedure is similar for both imaging modalities, based on threshold values that separate the intensity distribution into three distinct phases: matrix,

(a) Grayscale histogram from micrograph in Figure 5.

(b) Grayscale histogram from X-ray μ CT in Figure 4.

Figure 6: Grayscale intensity distribution with material phases: matrix, boundaries and fibres. Matrix and fibres are segmented and assigned values of 0 and 1, respectively, while boundary pixels are scaled linearly from 0 to 1 between the lower and upper thresholds.

boundaries and fibres. The boundary phase relates to pixels in the boundary between the fibres and matrix. The local V_f is estimated based on a semi-binary image where matrix pixels are assigned a value of 0, fibre pixels a value of 1, while the boundary phase acts as a ramping function between 0 and 1. Phases are separated using a lower and upper threshold as presented in Figure 6a. The grayscale intensity distributions can be described as linear combinations of three or two normal distributions for the micrographs and X-ray μ CT data, respectively. The lower threshold is defined at the intersection between the normal distributions constituting the neighbouring matrix and boundary phases. The upper threshold is determined by enforcing a condition that reduces the error between the image \bar{V}_f^{image} and the burn-off test result, $\bar{V}_f^{burn-off}$. The resulting semi-binary image yields a localised V_f distribution where all pixels have the property of pure matrix, fibre or a mix at the boundary.

The model used for predicting the compressive strength is based on homogenised material properties in a discretised field of finite elements with a lower spatial resolution than the image data. Applying, e.g., pure fibre properties to an element would, thus, falsely affect the surrounding region. Instead, a mean filter related to the fibre diam-

(a) V_f distribution for the micrograph in Figure 5b.

(b) V_f distribution from the X-ray μ CT data in the xz -plane presented in Figure 4.

Figure 7: Fibre volume fraction distributions using an averaging filter with a kernel width = $10D_f$.

eter, $D_f = 7 \mu\text{m}$, is applied, with a square filter kernel width approximately equal to $10D_f$. The sensitivity of the compressive strength predictions to changes in kernel size is presented in Appendix A in Figure A.22. There, it is shown that the stiffness increases with increasing kernel size. At the same time, the compressive strength prediction has a local minimum at a kernel size corresponding to the element size in the FE-model. Furthermore, it is shown that a constant V_f throughout the image predicts a higher stiffness and compressive strength. The resulting V_f distributions for the two imaging modalities using a kernel size of $10D_f$ are presented in Figure 7a and 7b for the micrograph and X-ray μCT data, respectively. Due to the higher contrast in the micrographs, a more localised V_f distribution is obtained with features like resin-rich regions. Conversely, the weak contrast between the constituents limits the X-ray μCT data, which ultimately yields a more smeared-out V_f distribution.

2.4.2. Fibre orientation distribution

Fibre orientation distributions are estimated using the structure tensor method for both imaging modalities and are based on the Python package implementation, *structure-tensor*, for 2D and 3D analysis. A short introduction to the 2D version of the method is presented here, where some intermediate calculations are omitted. A more detailed presentation of the calculation procedure is presented in the supplementary paper [17], and a complete description of the structure tensor method is described in [19]. For a given image, I , containing intensity information at all pixels, the structure tensor, \mathbf{S} , is calculated for every pixel using

$$\mathbf{S} = K_\rho * \left(\nabla I_\sigma (\nabla I_\sigma)^T \right) \quad , \quad (1)$$

where ∇I_σ is the intensity gradient vector and K_ρ is a Gaussian kernel used to integrate the gradient information by convolution (indicated by $*$). The subscripts, σ and ρ , refer to the standard deviations used in the Gaussian derivative and integration kernels, respectively. The *noise scale*, σ , is used for noise suppression in the calculation of the derivative, while the *integration scale*, ρ , defines the kernel size over which

the gradient information is integrated and should, thus, reflect the size of the features being analysed.

This work is based on the expression for σ and ρ suggested in [19] for analysing fibre structures in the X-ray data. The same ρ is used for the micrographs, but with an alternative σ due to less noise in the data. The two parameters used for the different imaging modalities are

$$\text{X-ray } \mu\text{CT:} \quad \rho = 4 \frac{r_f}{\sqrt{2}} \quad , \quad \sigma = \frac{\rho}{4} \quad , \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Micrograph:} \quad \rho = 4 \frac{r_f}{\sqrt{2}} \quad , \quad \sigma = 0.5 \quad , \quad (3)$$

where r_f is the fibre radius divided by the voxel or pixel size.

Following the calculation of the structure tensor, predominant orientations in the image are determined by finding the directions of least change in intensity. These directions are obtained through eigendecomposition of \mathbf{S} and yield a set of eigenvalues, $\lambda_1 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_n$ and correspondingly, mutually orthogonal eigenvectors, $\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_n$, where subscript $n = 2$ or $n = 3$ refers to the number of dimensions. The eigenvector \mathbf{r}_1 corresponds to the direction of least change in intensity and thus is considered the fibre orientation. For simplicity, the subscript for \mathbf{r}_1 is omitted in the following, $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_1$. Fibre orientations are calculated at every pixel using the unit eigenvector, \mathbf{r} , presented for 2D and 3D in Figure 8 and 9, respectively.

Two representations of fibre orientations are calculated for the X-ray μCT dataset. Orientations projected onto the xy - and xz -plane, ϕ_{xy} and ϕ_{xz} , respectively, are determined for visualisation. At the same time, azimuth, θ , and inclination angles, ϕ , are used as input for a rotation matrix in the 3D FE-model. Fibre orientations in the micrographs are based on through-thickness orientations, ϕ_{xy} , in the investigated xy -plane cut in the thickness direction, and are calculated using Equation 4.

$$\text{Projected orientations:} \quad \phi_{xy} = \arcsin(r_y) \quad , \quad \phi_{xz} = \arcsin(r_z) \quad , \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Inclination and azimuth:} \quad \phi = \arccos(r_x) \quad , \quad \theta = \arctan2(r_z, r_y) \quad . \quad (5)$$

The resulting fibre orientation distributions are presented for the micrograph and X-ray μ CT datasets in Figure 8 and 9, respectively.

The apparent drawback of the micrograph presented in Figure 8 is the 2D representation of orientations where features normal to the image plane are included as small elliptical shapes. These features are assigned a through-thickness orientation and are, thus, not captured correctly using micrographs. Wilhelmsson et al. [20] addressed this issue by filtering small discontinuous features from continuous fibres in the plane, resulting in an orientation distribution based on continuous fibres alone. As this work is based on a direct comparison between imaging modalities with the methods presented, we accept this deviation and mark it as a discussion point for potential improvements to the method.

The projected fibre orientation distribution from the X-ray μ CT data is presented for the xy - and xz -plane in Figure 9. Comparing the projected planes, it may be observed that fibre misalignments in the xy -plane are clustered. Furthermore, fibres appear closely packed, with only small areas of pure matrix, emphasising the need for

Figure 8: Through-thickness fibre orientation distribution, ϕ_{xy} , from micrograph ROI-11 in Figure 5.

Figure 9: Through-thickness and in-plane fibre orientation distributions, ϕ_{xy} and ϕ_{xz} , respectively from the C50 X-ray μ CT dataset in Figure 4.

high-resolution radiographs to improve the contrast between constituents when X-ray scanning using absorption contrast. However, fibres in the xz -plane move more freely, and the orientation distribution is more scattered. The fibre orientation histograms in Figure 8c and 9c present a similar through-thickness fibre orientation distribution, while the in-plane distribution for the X-ray μ CT data has a higher mean absolute orientation.

2.5. Finite element models and user-subroutine

Compressive strength predictions are performed in the commercial finite element software AbaqusTM. Schematic representations of the FE-models are presented in Figure 10 for micrographs in 2D and X-ray μ CT in 3D. The 3D model dimensions are defined with the same cross-sectional aspect ratio as the gauge section of the pure compression test presented in Section 2.7, with a depth to height ratio of $D/H = 6/5$. The model width, W , is constrained to an aspect ratio of $W/H = 3/2$, to mitigate challenges with Euler buckling during compressive loading. The exact model dimensions for the 3D model are presented in Figure 4. The same H and W dimensions are used for the 2D model for direct comparison between compressive strength predictions.

The models resemble a pure compression test with an applied displacement, d_x , along the x -axis and fixed displacements, $[d_x, d_y, (d_z)] = 0$, on the opposing edge/surface. Boundary conditions are applied so the plane/volume can expand in other directions. The compressive strength predictions are based on the non-linear constitutive model presented in Section 2.6. The constitutive model is based on homogenised matrix and fibre material properties and does not include a length scale. It is well-known that

Figure 10: Schematic representation of FE-models for the two imaging modalities. Both models are constrained at one end with displacement boundary conditions, $d = 0$, with directional subscripts, $[x, y, z]$. A displacement, d_x , is applied to the opposing surface.

such a model will lead to a fundamentally mesh-dependent solution, see Tvergaard and Needleman [21] and Sørensen et al. [22]. For the specific case, a mesh sensitivity study is presented in Appendix A in Figure A.23 for the 2D model, where it is shown that an increase in element size results in increased compressive strength predictions, similar to the observation presented in [22]. To account for this dependency, the element size is defined as a typical kink band width experimentally or numerically observed in the literature. This has been reported to be around $10\times$ the fibre diameter [2]. Both models are discretised using a structured mesh with square/cubic elements, an element size of $10D_f = 70\ \mu\text{m}$, and a quadratic element formulation with full integration. The 2D model is based on the solid 8-node plane strain element, *CPE8*, with 3^2 integration points, and the 3D model is based on the solid 20-node element, *C3D20*, with 3^3 integration points. Failure predictions are associated with kink band formation, where a limit load instability defines the compressive strength, followed by snap-back instability. The Riks arc-length method is used in a static step to capture this effect.

2.5.1. Field quantity implementation

The field quantities presented in Section 2.4 are implemented in the FE-model through integration point-wise mapping. A complete and detailed description of this procedure is available in the supplementary work [17], and only the essential details are included here.

Fibre orientations are included in the FE-mesh using the *ORIENT* user-subroutine in AbaqusTM. For each integration point, the local material orientation is updated according to a transformation matrix, \mathbf{T} ,

$$2D : \quad \mathbf{T} = \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{z}}(\phi_{xy}) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi_{xy} & -\sin \phi_{xy} & 0 \\ \sin \phi_{xy} & \cos \phi_{xy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

$$3D : \quad \mathbf{T} = \mathbf{R}_x(\theta)\mathbf{R}_z(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi & -\sin \phi & 0 \\ \sin \phi & \cos \phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{R}_i is a rotation matrix about axis $i \in [x, y, z]$, and orientations included in the trigonometric functions are defined in Equation 4 and 5 for the 2D and 3D models, respectively.

Similar to the local orientation, the local V_f is used as input to the non-linear constitutive model presented in the following section. Material properties are, thus, updated for each integration point according to the mapped V_f .

2.6. Non-linear constitutive model

The User-defined Material model, UMAT, used for predicting compressive failure associated with kink band formation is described in the following, and refers to the input box **(b)** presented in Figure 2. Two versions of the non-linear constitutive model are used in this work. A 2D version developed by Christoffersen and Jensen [14] was used for studying compressive failure of unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites, and an extended 3D version by Skovsgaard and Jensen [15]. A summary of the 2D version is presented in the following, while an overview of the 3D version is presented in an earlier work by the authors [13].

Figure 11 presents a layered representation of a fibre-reinforced composite material using a Representative Volume Element (RVE) based on the 2D constitutive model.

Figure 11: Layered representation of a fibre-reinforced composite material with an RVE containing fibre and matrix material with the following relation, $V = V_f + V_m$.

The RVE comprises a volume, V , with unit thickness, and volume fractions V_f and V_m for fibre and matrix, respectively. The model is based on the assumptions that deformation patterns are long-waved relative to the fibre diameter, $\lambda \gg a$, that perfect bonding between the fibres and matrix exists, and that an elastic-plastic constitutive law is used to describe the behaviour of individual constituents.

The constitutive model is presented using index notation. The non-linear behaviour of the fibre-reinforced composite is described using a rate-dependent constitutive law in the form

$$\dot{t}_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \dot{u}_{l,k} \quad i, j, k, l = \{1, 2\} \quad , \quad (8)$$

where \dot{t}_{ij} are components of nominal stress rates, C_{ijkl} are components of the tensor of the nominal moduli and \dot{u}_i are displacement rates (velocities) where the comma notation, $(\cdot)_{,i}$ denotes partial derivatives with respect to spatial coordinates. The summation convention is adopted here for repeated indices.

Based on knowledge about the elastic-plastic behaviour of the constituents, the same constitutive law can be used for the constituents with the superscript $(\cdot)^c$, which represents either $(\cdot)^f$ or $(\cdot)^m$ for the fibre or matrix, respectively

$$\dot{t}_{ij}^c = C_{ijkl}^c \dot{u}_{l,k}^c \quad . \quad (9)$$

The derivation of the tensor of nominal moduli for the composite is performed in two parts. First, a general relation is established for each constituent, resulting in a set of constitutive tensors based on the elastic-plastic properties. Secondly, the composite constitutive tensor is formalised using constitutive tensors for the fibre and matrix following the assumptions described earlier, resulting in a homogenised constitutive model. The derivation of the constitutive tensors is rather long and outside the scope of this work. A detailed derivation is presented in the original work by Christoffersen and Jensen [14].

The tensor of nominal moduli for the constituents, C_{ijkl}^c , is a function of the stress state in the material and the elastic-plastic tangent moduli, L_{ijkl}^c . The version used here is based on J_2 -deformation theory with a model proposed by Stören and Rice

[23], and uses an elastic-plastic tangent moduli dependent on the bulk modulus, K , and the secant and tangent shear moduli, G_s and G_t , respectively

$$K = \frac{E}{3(1-2\nu)}; \quad \frac{1}{G_s} = \frac{3}{E_s} - \frac{1-2\nu}{E}; \quad \frac{1}{G_t} = \frac{1}{E_t} - \frac{1-2\nu}{E} \quad , \quad (10)$$

where E and ν are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the constituents, respectively, while E_s and E_t are the secant and tangent moduli, respectively, determined from the Ramberg-Osgood relation

$$\varepsilon_{eq} = \frac{\sigma_{eq}}{E} + \frac{3}{7} \frac{\sigma_y}{E} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{\sigma_y} \right)^n \quad , \quad (11)$$

where ε_{eq} is the equivalent uniaxial logarithmic strain, σ_{eq} is the equivalent uniaxial true stress, while σ_y and n are the reference yield stress and hardening exponent, respectively. The secant and tangent moduli are determined using

$$\frac{1}{E_s} = \frac{\varepsilon_{eq}}{\sigma_{eq}}; \quad \frac{1}{E_t} = \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{eq}}{\partial \sigma_{eq}} \quad . \quad (12)$$

Assuming isotropic material properties for the constituents, the input material parameters in the constitutive tensor, C_{ijkl}^c , can be characterised using a simple uniaxial tensile or compression test of the constituents. Constitutive relations for the fibre and matrix are thus established as

$$t_{ij}^f = C_{ijkl}^f \dot{u}_{l,k}^f; \quad t_{ij}^m = C_{ijkl}^m \dot{u}_{l,k}^m \quad . \quad (13)$$

The derivation of the composite constitutive tensor, C_{ijkl} , is based on the assumptions presented for the RVE in Figure 11. The assumption of a long-waved deformation pattern requires that lines parallel with the fibres share a common stretching and rotation

$$\dot{u}_{i,1} = \dot{u}_{i,1}^f = \dot{u}_{i,1}^m \quad . \quad (14)$$

The assumption of perfect bonding between the constituents requires that lines parallel with fibres transmit identical tractions

$$t_{2i} = t_{2i}^f = t_{2i}^m \quad . \quad (15)$$

Overall compatibility is established by enforcing scaled velocities of the constituents using volume fractions

$$\dot{u}_{i,2} = V_f \dot{u}_{i,2}^f + V_m \dot{u}_{i,2}^m \quad (16)$$

Similarly, equilibrium is ensured using scaled tractions in the constituents

$$\dot{t}_{1i} = V_f \dot{t}_{1i}^f + V_m \dot{t}_{1i}^m \quad . \quad (17)$$

Following the derivation presented in [14], the composite constitutive relation in Equation 8 is established, where the constitutive tensor, C_{ijkl} , is a function of the fibre volume fraction, V_f , and the fibre and matrix constitutive tensors, C_{ijkl}^f and C_{ijkl}^m , respectively.

The non-linear constitutive model is included in the FE-model as a user-defined material model. There, nominal stress rates, \dot{t}_{ij} are related to Cauchy stress rates, $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$, following the relation presented in [14], where Cauchy stresses, σ_{ij} , and the constituent moduli, C_{ijkl}^c , are updated through incremental loading. Input parameters for the UMAT include the fibre volume fraction, V_f , and the elastic-plastic material properties for the fibre and matrix material.

2.7. Experimental characterisation of material properties

The input parameters required for the non-linear constitutive model are presented below. Elastic-plastic material properties are determined from uniaxial testing of the constituents, where the Ramberg-Osgood relation presented in Equation 11 is fitted to the experimental data using

$$\varepsilon_{eq} = \frac{\sigma_{eq}}{E} + \frac{3}{7} \frac{\sigma^{RO}}{E} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{\sigma^{RO}} \right)^{n^{RO}} \quad . \quad (18)$$

In this work, the elastic modulus, E , is measured in the strain range [0.05, 0.25]%, and σ^{RO} and n^{RO} are fitting parameters.

2.7.1. Matrix properties

Ideally, the material properties of the constituents should be characterised based on the dominant stress state during compressive failure of the composite. Kink band

failure is associated with shear instability of the fibres due to matrix plasticity, where shear stresses are induced due to inclined fibres relative to the load direction. In the work by Zike et al. [24], it was shown that the equivalent stress-strain curve for a V-notch shear test specimen [25] and a tensile test specimen [26], coincides for an epoxy resin system. Taking advantage of this relation, a series of five tensile test specimens was used to quantify the elastic-plastic properties of the cured matrix material based on ISO-527-2 standard [26] with the test specimen presented in Figure 12a, and the resulting equivalent stress-strain curves in Figure 13a.

2.7.2. Pultruded profile and fibre properties

The fibre volume fraction of the carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profile was measured using a burn-off test of 10 samples with a size of $15 \times 5 \times 15 \text{ mm}^3$. A burn-off sequence of 450°C for 2 hours was used, where the samples were weighed before and after. Based on the fibre and matrix density of 1.8 and 1.14 g/cm^3 , respectively, the mean fibre volume fraction was measured to $\bar{V}_f^{\text{burn-off}} = 0.67 \pm 0.004$ with a void content of 0.2% .

The elastic-plastic properties of the carbon fibres are characterised using a uniaxial compression test of the UDCFPP. Ideally, a direct compression test of a single carbon fibre is preferred as the results are less affected by the fibre orientations in the sample. However, due to the low degree of fibre misalignment presented in Section 2.4.2, a deviation in the constitutive response is judged insignificant and thus accepted.

A series of 5 compression test specimens were tested according to ISO-14126 [27] using the test specimen in Figure 12b and a test fixture introducing compressive loading through combined shear and end loading. The specimen design is based on a design iteration in the work by Dubary et al. [3]. They seek to design a compression test specimen capable of achieving gauge failure for thick UDCFPP by tapering the composite and tabbing material to mitigate the risk of load introduction failure.

All results presented in this work have been normalised per a confidentiality agreement. This normalisation does not affect the validity of the analysis; rather, it en-

Figure 12: Test specimens.

hances the clarity of the discussion and conclusions, as the differences between the two approaches become more pronounced. Stress-strain results are normalised with respect to a reference strength from the direct compression test of the UDCFPP. The resulting stress-strain response for the UDCFPP is presented in Figure 13b, where the average failure strength, σ_{ref} , and strain, ε_{ref} , are highlighted as the reference for normalisation of all results in this work.

The elastic-plastic fibre properties are back-calculated from the UDCFPP compression test, based on the matrix properties characterised in Figure 13a, the $\bar{V}_f^{burn-off}$ from the burn-off test, and under the assumption that fibres are perfectly aligned with the principal load direction. The non-linear stress-strain relation for the fibres (σ_f, ε_f) is determined using the *iso-strain* assumption of common stretching of the constituents loaded along the fibre direction, $\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_m$, where the subscripts refer to the composite, fibres and matrix, respectively. Using the Ramberg-Osgood equation (18) to describe the matrix strain, ε_m , the following can be used to solve for the matrix stress iteratively, σ_m , based on the measured strain from the direct compression test of the UDCFPP, ε_c ,

$$\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_m \quad \rightarrow \quad \varepsilon_f = \frac{\sigma_m}{E_m} + \frac{3}{7} \frac{\sigma_m^{RO}}{E_m} \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_m^{RO}} \right)^{n_m^{RO}} . \quad (19)$$

Here the elastic-plastic matrix properties ($E_m, \sigma_m^{RO}, n_m^{RO}$) are determined from the tensile test of the matrix material. Subsequently, the rule-of-mixture for stresses along the fibre direction can be used to determine the fibre stress, σ_f , based on the fibre volume fraction, $\bar{V}_f^{burn-off}$, the measured composite stress, σ_c , and the matrix stress, σ_m , determined in equation (19).

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f \bar{V}_f^{burn-off} + \sigma_m (1 - \bar{V}_f^{burn-off}) \quad \rightarrow \quad \sigma_f = \frac{\sigma_c - \sigma_m (1 - \bar{V}_f^{burn-off})}{\bar{V}_f^{burn-off}} \quad , \quad (20)$$

Figure 13b presents the resulting non-linear stress-strain relation for fibres.

(a) Tensile test of cured matrix.

(b) Direct compression test of UDCFPP (EXP) with Ramberg-Osgood fit (Fit) and normalised reference strength (Ref). Back calculated fibre response (Est) and corresponding Ramberg-Osgood fit (Fit).

(c) Comparison of Ramberg-Osgood fits for the constituents and the UDCFPP.

Figure 13: Elastic-plastic response of the UDCFPP and constituents presented with true stress, σ_t , and logarithmic strain, ε_{ln} . Normalised results with respect to the average failure strength and strain σ_{ref} and ε_{ref} , respectively, from the UDCFPP compression test.

Table 2: Normalised input parameters for the non-linear constitutive model with constituent properties based on the Ramberg-Osgood relation in equation (18) and Poisson’s ratios. Values are normalised using the reference strength and strain, σ_{ref} , and ε_{ref} , respectively, where the E-moduli are normalised using the secant modulus from the reference properties, $E_{ref} = \sigma_{ref}/\varepsilon_{ref}$. Carbon fibre properties estimated from the matrix and UDCFPP test results with $\bar{V}_f^{burn-off} = 0.67$. UDCFPP material properties are included for reference but not used as input for the UMAT.

Material properties	E/E_{ref} [-]	σ_{RO}/σ_{ref} [MPa]	n_{RO} [-]	ν [-]
Matrix	0.01	0.05	3.64	0.4
Carbon fibres	1.62	2.77	3.57	0.26
UDCFPP	1.09	1.87	3.57	-

A comparison between the estimated constitutive response of the fibres and those measured from the UDCFPP and matrix test is presented in Figure 13c. The corresponding properties are listed in Table 2 and used in the user-subroutine presented in Section 2.6 for predicting the compressive strength.

3. Results

The following compressive strength predictions are based on fibre distributions estimated from the data presented in Figure 3 and 5. All results are normalised using the reference strength and strain to failure, σ_{ref} and ε_{ref} , respectively, measured from the direct compression test presented in Section 2.7. The non-linear stress-strain response for a 2D and 3D FE-model is presented in Figure 14. A clear difference in constitutive response is observed, where the higher stiffness of the 2D-model is attributed to the plain strain assumption. The compressive strength is defined at the limit load instability **(a)**. A snap-back response closely traces the original loading path **(b)** until strain localises at lower stress levels **(c)**. A similar behaviour for the 3D-model is observed with the limit load instability at **(d)**; however, snap-back behaviour appears locked to the original loading path **(e)** and strain localisation similar to the 2D-model is not obtained as the arc-length step size approaches zero.

Figure 14: Non-linear stress-strain response normalised using $(\sigma_{ref}, \varepsilon_{ref})$. Engineering stress, σ_e , and strain ε_e , are calculated from reaction forces and displacements, respectively, at the surface with applied displacements (see Figure 10). Points (a)-(c) and (e)-(d) mark characteristic events for the ROI-11 2D-model and C50 3D-model, respectively.

The simulations were performed on a Linux cluster node with an Intel Xeon E5-2667 v3 CPU (8 cores, 3.2 GHz) and 128 GB of RAM. The computation time for the 2D-model was 3 min for a solution at the limit load instability and 20 min for a fully developed kink band. Similarly, the 3D-model obtained a solution after 6.5 h and 19 h,

Figure 15: Strain localisation results from the ROI-11 2D-model in Figure 14. Orientation distribution used as input for the 2D-model is plotted with the maximum principal strains, ε_{max} , obtained from the FE integration points with values larger than a threshold.

respectively, i.e., most of the computation time is spent on kink band propagation during the unstable snap-back behaviour.

Figure 15 presents the predicted failure sequence for the 2D-model, where strain localisation is represented using maximum principal strains above a threshold of 1%, exported from the FE integration points. Strain localisation is observed from the bottom edge of the image after the limit load instability in Figure 14b. The snap-back behaviour is triggered by large rotations of the elements close to a region with fibre misalignments, where the surrounding material releases energy into the damage zone

Figure 16: Strain localisation results from the C50 3D-model in Figure 14 . Projected orientations are plotted for the xy - and xz -planes, while the cross section, yz , is presented using the through-thickness angle ϕ_{xy} . Maximum principal strains obtained from the FE integration points with values larger than a threshold strain are plotted on top of the orientation data.

by expanding and further rotating the spinning elements. The unstable process ultimately results in a fully developed through-thickness kink band at the final stress-strain condition in Figure 14c.

Figure 16 presents the associated failure location from the 3D model, where strain localisation is observed near a region of highly misaligned fibres from the surface. However, the initialised kink band region does not propagate further through the volume before the arc-length step size approaches zero, and the FE-model terminates. Even though the kink band does not propagate fully through the width and thickness, the 3D model can predict the initiation of compressive failure associated with localised fibre misalignments in the volume.

All compressive strength predictions from both imaging modalities are presented with the experimental results from the compression test of a UDCFPP in Figure 17 and Table 3. The stress-strain response of the 2D- and 3D-models is presented with representative curves, while all compressive strength predictions are included as a scatter plot. Compressive strength predictions based on the 2D micrographs are close to the

Figure 17: Normalised compressive strength predictions from 2D- and 3D-models using micrograph and X-ray μ CT data, respectively. Experimental results from the pure compression test in Section 2.7 are included as a scatter plot.

Table 3: Normalised experimental and numerical compressive strength results with associated fibre orientation characteristics. Variation in data is presented as \pm one standard deviation.

Data	$\bar{\phi}$ [°]	$\overline{ \phi_{xy} }$ [°]	$\overline{ \phi_{xz} }$ [°]	E/E_{ref} [-]	$\varepsilon_{fail}/\varepsilon_{ref}$ [-]	$\sigma_{fail}/\sigma_{ref}$ [-]
Experimental	-	-	-	1.09 ± 0.004	1.0 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.1
Micrographs (2D)	-	0.45 ± 0.07	-	1.14 ± 0.012	0.94 ± 0.03	1.03 ± 0.03
C50 (3D)	0.78	0.42	0.56	1.09	1.99	1.69
C75 (3D)	0.79	0.43	0.58	1.09	1.92	1.65
S50 (3D)	0.91	0.44	0.70	1.08	1.67	1.50
S75 (3D)	0.93	0.44	0.73	1.08	1.68	1.50

experimentally measured compressive strength results, but with a Young’s modulus, $E \approx 5\%$ higher.

The elastic-plastic constitutive response of the 3D models is in good agreement with the experimental results, with Young’s moduli estimated within one to two standard deviations lower than the experimental results. The consistency in lower stiffness predictions may be described by the discrepancy between fibre distributions in the modelled sub-volumes and the full thickness of the profile tested experimentally.

All 3D compressive strength predictions are 50-69% higher than experimentally measured results. Strength predictions are clustered according to the sub-volume scan position through the thickness, with central scans obtaining the highest compressive strengths.

Finally, results from Figure 17 and Table 3 are compared with respect to the average orientation distribution, and the closed-form expression for the compressive strength of fibre-reinforced composites, as suggested by Budiansky and Fleck [2].

$$\sigma_{fail} = \frac{G}{1 + \overline{|\phi_{ij}|}/\gamma_y} \quad , \quad (21)$$

$$\gamma_y = \frac{\tau_y}{G}, \quad G/E_{ref} = 0.012, \quad \tau_y = \frac{\sigma_y}{\sqrt{3}}, \quad \sigma_y/\sigma_{ref} = 0.033 \quad .$$

Equation (21) estimates the compressive strength, σ_{fail} , based on the mean absolute

Figure 18: Normalised compressive strength predictions with respect to mean absolute fibre misalignments and compared with Equation (21).

orientation, $|\overline{\phi_{ij}}|$, and the elastic-plastic shear properties of the composite. Here, G is the composite shear modulus calculated using the rules of mixtures with the material properties presented in Section 2.7, and the yield stress, σ_y , is taken as the 0.2% offset yield strength of the matrix material presented in Figure 13a. Figure 18 shows that all 2D-model predictions are close to Equation (21), while 3D-model predictions are significantly higher.

4. Discussion

4.1. Prediction accuracy

Based on the comparison between experimental results and 2D-model predictions in Figure 17, it appears that the 2D micrograph modelling approach is sufficient for characterising the compressive strength based on through-thickness fibre orientations. Furthermore, the 2D-model predictions are in the same range as the closed-form expression presented by Budiansky and Fleck [2] in Equation (21), based on a single characteristic fibre orientation (see Figure 18).

However, all compression test samples failed prematurely under the tabbing region as presented in Figure 1b, where a stress concentration exists from the transition be-

tween the tabbing region and the gauge section. All measured compression strength results are considered lower than the actual material compressive strength of the UD-CFPP, and thus, the 2D-model results are considered under predictions. The low strength predictions may be caused by the assumption of constant fibre orientation along the 3rd axis out of the image plane, which is not the case for a UDCFPF as presented with X-ray μ CT data. This emphasises that the pristine UDCFPF material cannot be simplified into 2D, which is typically the case for other fabric-based composite materials like the NCF presented in [16]. Due to the challenges in characterising the compressive strength experimentally, the accuracy of the 3D-model predictions cannot be quantified. Still, it may instead be regarded as a potential for the compressive strength.

4.2. Representable field of view

Figure 19 presents a histogram of projected fibre orientation distributions for all four X-ray μ CT scans. A comparison between the through-thickness fibre orientations, ϕ_{xy} , does not reveal any significant difference between the central and surface scans. In contrast, the in-plane orientations, ϕ_{xz} , differ slightly with a mean absolute orientation of 0.57° and 0.72° for the central and surface scans, respectively. It is, however, debatable whether a comparatively minor variation in the overall in-plane fibre

Figure 19: Projected orientation distribution histograms for all four scans in Figure 3.

misalignment characteristic is capable of producing such a pronounced reduction in compressive strength prediction.

Instead it is argued that local variations in the volume with large fibre misalignments relative to the distributions in Figure 19, govern compressive failure. From the 3D strain localisation plot presented in Figure 16, failure initiation appears at the surface close to a region of large fibre misalignments. Similar to the observation given in [28], the bifurcation stress is lower for a state of plane-stress at the surface of the specimen, and thus, more likely to fail at the surface. The orientation distribution close to the failure location includes significant fibre misalignments far outside the normal distribution presented in Figure 19. This indicates that local fibre misalignments govern compressive failure in the UDCFPP with a small volume percentage relative to the total volume of the scanned sample. Figure 20 presents an alternative representation of the fibre orientation distribution, where the projected orientations are averaged for every y -coordinate and plotted through the thickness.

Figure 20: Orientation distributions through the thickness. Projected orientations, ϕ_{xy} and ϕ_{xz} , are averaged for all y -coordinates and plotted through the thickness, where $y = 0$ corresponds to the surface of the profile. Failure locations associated with the corresponding fibre orientations.

From this, it may be observed that the through-thickness fibre orientation distribution, ϕ_{xy} , is relatively low with small variations from the mean. A similar distribution is presented for the 2D micrographs, but with a significant variation, which may be attributed to the out-of-image objects and the fact that only a single plane is considered. In contrast, the in-plane orientations, ϕ_{xz} , from the X-ray μ CT are more scattered and with pronounced fibre misalignments towards the surface of the profile, which supports the relative difference in compressive strength predictions with surface scans yielding lower strength values. Furthermore, two predictions have been highlighted at the corresponding failure locations associated with large through-thickness and in-plane fibre misalignments.

Figure 21 presents the corresponding V_f distribution for both imaging modalities. The large variation in V_f for the 2D micrograph is partially caused by the higher resolution and contrast of the images, where a localised V_f distribution is obtained. The same failure locations are presented for the V_f distributions of the X-ray μ CT data, where a correlation between large fibre misalignments and reduced V_f is observed. Considering the results from the surface and central X-ray μ CT scans, it is clear that the sub-volumes cannot be viewed as representable volume elements, due to the significant difference in fibre distribution and compressive strength predictions. The sub-volume size should, thus, cover more than half the profile thickness, assuming

Figure 21: V_f distribution through the thickness. V_f is averaged for all y -coordinates and plotted through the thickness, where $y = 0$ corresponds to the surface of the profile. Failure locations associated with the corresponding V_f .

that the fibre distribution is symmetric about the mid-plane of the UDCFPP. The difference in failure predictions for the two imaging modalities demonstrates the importance of capturing local variations in the fibre orientation distribution when predicting compressive failure for UDCFPPs. The dominating orientation of the fibre misalignments triggering compressive failure is unknown before image acquisition, and capturing key features in the volume using optical microscopy or other 2D equivalent methods would require extensive efforts without a guarantee of finding the representative features.

5. Summary and Conclusion

Two approaches were demonstrated to predict the compressive strength of unidirectional fibre-reinforced composite materials based on realistic fibre distributions. Volumetric and planar fibre distributions are determined from X-ray μ CT and optical microscopy data, respectively, of a Unidirectional Carbon Fibre-reinforced Pultruded Profile (UDCFPP). Fibre volume fraction and orientation distributions are determined from the image data and used as input for a finite element model. A non-linear constitutive material model is implemented through a user-defined material model to predict the compressive strength associated with kink band formation. The two modelling strategies are compared with experimental results from a pure compression test of a UDCFPP, where all samples failed below the tabbing region. The 2D-modelling approach based on micrographs is a fast and easily accessible method. All compressive strength predictions are close to the experimentally measured strengths; however, both results are considered low relative to the real material strength. In contrast, the 3D-modelling approach based on X-ray μ CT data is more cumbersome concerning data acquisition, processing and ultimately simulation time. The 3D-model predictions are based on sub-volumes at the surface and near the centre of the UDCFPP. In-plane fibre misalignments are generally more pronounced for all sub-volumes, where the magnitude and variation increase when approaching the surface of the profile. Compressive strength predictions range from 50-69% higher than

the conservative experimental results, where the larger fibre misalignment characteristics of the surface sub-volumes yield the lowest strength predictions.

Even though the two imaging modalities yield similar estimates for through-thickness fibre misalignment, the micrograph approach has the obvious limitation of neglecting in-plane (out-of-image) fibre orientations, which ultimately showed the most significant variation through the volume. Furthermore, compressive failure was associated with small regions of large fibre misalignments, deviating significantly from the global fibre orientation distribution. The location and characteristics of these regions were unknown before X-ray scanning, and capturing similar features with optical microscopy would require extensive work without a guarantee of locating them. It is thus concluded that the 2D micrograph approach is insufficient for predicting the compressive behaviour of a pristine UDCFPP, where the characteristic fibre distribution is inherently three-dimensional and cannot be simplified into 2D, like, e.g., Non-crimp fabrics. Finally, increasing the sub-volume size of the X-ray μ CT scans to a minimum of half the thickness is recommended. This will include most characteristic features of the fibre distribution through the thickness, and result in more representative compressive strength predictions for the UDCFPP profile.

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Author contributions

O V. Ferguson: Writing – original draft, Conceptualisation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Resources, Visualisation, Software. **J. B. Jørgensen:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualisation, Supervision. **L P. Mikkelsen:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualisation, Supervision.

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Appendix A. Sensitivity studies

Figure A.22 presents the sensitivity of the predicted compressive behaviour to changes in the kernel size used to determine the distributed fibre volume fraction, V_f . Kernel sizes ranging from 4 to 14 fibre diameters, D_f , are compared against a version with constant V_f for the entire image. It is observed that a distributed V_f yields a lower calculated E-modulus and compressive strength than the constant V_f . Stiffness increases for increasing kernel sizes, while the compressive strength predictions have a local minimum at the kernel size matching the element size used in the finite element model.

Figure A.22: Sensitivity of 2D model predictions to changes in kernel size used for estimating the V_f distribution by calculating the local average

Figure A.23 presents the sensitivity of the compressive strength predictions to changes in element size. The change in spatial resolution of the elements cause a variation in the calculated E-modulus. Compressive strength predictions increase for increasing element sizes, corresponding to the observation in [22], for idealised fibre orientations. The strength predictions do not converge to a strength value, which is expected due to the lack of a length scale in the homogenised composite description.

Figure A.23: The fundamental mesh dependency of 2D model predictions.